

UNDERWATER EXPLOSIVE LOADING OF E-GLASS / VINYL ESTER COMPOSITE PLATES: CORRELATION OF EXPERIMENTS AND SIMULATIONS

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1 Abstract

The transient response of an E-Glass / Vinyl-Ester composite material subjected to underwater explosive loading has been studied. The work consists of experimental testing, utilizing a water filled conical shock tube and computational simulations, utilizing the commercially available LS-DYNA finite element code. The composite plates are 0/90 biaxial laminates with a thickness of approximately 1.3mm. The plates are round disks with elliptically curved mid-sections. The transient response of the plates is captured in real time through the use of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system. The DIC data and computational results show a high level of correlation for both the out-of-plane deflection and velocity histories.

2 Introduction

Composite materials have been widely used in a variety of applications in the marine, automotive, and transportation industries. These materials offer the advantages of high strength to weight ratios, reduced maintenance costs, and improved corrosion resistance. Recently, there has been an increased interest in composite materials for use in military applications including land vehicles, advanced ship hull designs, and submarine components. The use of these materials in wartime environments requires that they not only be able to withstand the loads produced by everyday use but also those imparted from explosions and high speed projectile impacts. The level of understanding of the response of these materials at these high loading rates is not as established as that under static conditions. Specifically, the ability to predict the load carrying capability of these materials after a shock loading event. This leads to an inherent conservative approach to be taken when these structures are designed and constructed.

The response of composite materials subjected to shock and impact loading has been studied over a wide range of loading rates. The response of E-Glass and Carbon based composite laminates under shock and explosive loading has been presented by Tekalur et al [1]. LeBlanc et al [2] have studied the effects of shock loading on three-dimensional woven composite materials. Recently, there has been an increased interest in the study of the effect of shock loading on sandwich structures. These studies include the effects of shock and impact loading conditions (Jackson et al [3], Schubel et al [4]). The finite element modeling of damage in composites has been performed primarily on models simulating strain rates up to those representing drop test experiments with some work performed at the high strain rate regimes expected in shock loading. Material models are continually being implemented and refined in existing commercial finite element codes (O'Daniel et al [5], McGregor et al [6]). Batra and Hassan [7] studied the response of composites to UNDEX loading through numerical simulations; however, there are no comparisons to experimental results. LeBlanc et al. [8] have presented a modeling methodology which simulates composite plates subjected to underwater explosive loading with comparisons to both the transient strain response as well as post mortem damage.

3 Composite Material

The material used in this study is an E-Glass / Vinyl ester composite with a 0°- 90° biaxial layup. The areal weight of the dry fabric is 0.406 kg/m² (12 oz/yd²). The panels which are utilized in the study consist of 3 plies of the fabric, with each ply oriented in the same direction. The panels are manufactured using the vacuum infusion process with a vinyl ester

resin, AOC Hydropel R015-AAG-00. The finished part thickness is 1.37 mm (0.054 in.) and has a fiber content of 62% by weight.

The geometry of the plates consists of a curved midsection with a flat boundary as shown in figure 1. The convex face of the plate represents the mold line in the manufacturing and has a radius of curvature of 18.28 cm (7.2 in.), an outer diameter of 26.54 cm (10.45 in.), and the curved portion of the plate is 22.86 cm (9 in.) in diameter.

4 Test Method

A conical shock tube (CST) facility located at the Naval Undersea Warfare Center, Division Newport was utilized in the shock loading of the composite materials. The shock tube is a horizontally mounted, water filled tube with a conical internal shape, Figure 2. The pressure shock wave is initiated by the detonation of an explosive charge at the breech end of the tube (left side of figure) which then proceeds down the length of the tube. Peak shock pressures from 10.3 MPa (1500 lb/in²) to 20.6 MPa (3000 lb/in²) can be obtained depending on the amount of explosive charge. The specimens are air backed, held with fully clamped edges, and are mounted with the convex surface towards the incoming shock fronts. This is chosen so that the test will represent geometries commonly used in underwater applications with curved surfaces typically facing into the the fluid (i.e. submersible vehicle hull forms).

The Digital Image Correlation (DIC) technique is used to capture the transient response of the back face (dry) of the plates. DIC is a non-intrusive, optical technique for capturing the full field, transient response of the panels through the use of high speed photography and specialized software. Two high speed digital cameras, Photron SA1, are positioned behind the shock tube. The use of two cameras allows for the out-of-plane behavior to be captured. A frame rate of 20,000 fps was used with an inter-frame time of 50 μ s.

5 Finite Element Modeling

Finite element modeling of the experiment has been performed utilizing the Ls-Dyna code available from the Livermore Software Technology Corporation

(LSTC). The composite plate in the simulations is modeled using shell elements. Each shell layer represents the mid-surface a 0° and 90° combined ply. An orthotropic material definition capable of modeling the progressive failure is utilized. The material model considers failure due to any of several criterion including tension / compression in the longitudinal and transverse directions, compression in the through thickness direction, and through thickness shear. Delamination damage is considered and is taken into account through the use of a surface-to-surface tiebreak contact definition. The pressure load is applied as a plane wave at the location of the test pressure transducer and is identical to the profile that was measured during the test.

6. Finite Element Simulation Results

The finite element simulation of the shock tube testing allows for a visual full field representation of the interaction between the pressure wave and the composite plate. The pressure field in the fluid as it interacts with and loads the plate is shown in the left side of figure 3. The associated plate response is shown in the right side of the figure. The loading of the plate and the associated response can be separated into two distinct time regimes. Where the pressure wave interacts with the plate over 0.2 ms, the plate does not start to deform until the wave is nearly fully reflected and takes approximately 5.5 ms to complete. The plate deformation in the current study can be described as a full inversion, taking approximately 5.5 ms to complete.

7 Simulation Correlation to Test

The displacement and velocity data that was captured during the experiments is used as a basis to correlate and validate the finite element model results. The DIC technique allows for the extraction of a large amount of data from the surface of the plates. The two variables that are used for correlation of the simulations to the experiments are the out of plane displacement and velocity. Time histories are extracted from the DIC data for the center point of the plates, figure 4. The displacement comparison shows that the experiment and simulation results agree nearly exactly until 2.5 ms at which point the displacement in the experiment

occurs slightly faster than the simulation. In the velocity comparison, it is seen that there is an initial out-of-plane velocity of just less than 20 m/s which then settles to about 10 m/s for the remaining duration of the event. In addition to the point wise time histories, full field comparisons are made between the experiment and simulations. A comparison of the full field, out of plane displacement evolution is shown in figure 5. The DIC strain measurements made during this study show that the in-plane strain rates are on the order of 10-50/s. Although the through thickness strain rate was not measured it is expected to be higher than the in-plane strain rate.

8 Conclusions

A conical shock tube has been used to study the response of curved E-Glass / Vinyl ester composite panels subjected to underwater shock loading. The material is a bi-axial laminate with fibers balanced in the 0 and 90 degree directions. The round plates are curved in shape with the convex surface oriented towards the incoming shock front with fully clamped boundaries. A 3D Digital Image Correlation system is used to capture the full field, transient response of the back (dry) surface of the plates. The displacement and velocity data for the center point exhibit good correlation when comparing the test and simulation results. The full field displacement evolution is also shown to agree between the experiment and the simulations. This work has shown the ability of Ls-Dyna to realistically model the behavior of a composite material under shock loading conditions. This work has served to show that computational tools can serve to support experimental test results.

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Fig. 1 – Composite Plate Geometry (Section View)

Fig. 2 – Conical shock tube schematic

Fig. 5 – Full Field Deformation Comparison of Experiment and Simulation

Fig. 3 (a) Fluid Structure Interaction, (b) Plate Deformation Progression

Fig. 4 –Time history comparison of experiment and simulation